

ISSUES, COMMON ERRORS AND BARRIERS TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF AGILITY IN AN ORGANIZATIONAL CONTEXT

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Abstract

Agility in organizational context (AOc) is a new concept in management literature and carries great importance for the companies operating in uncertain business environments as Romania and everywhere else. Many of the previous approaches to process development or transformation focus on practices and processes that organizational actors should learn. Based on our research we list a number of predictors expected to be on the attention list of organizations' leadership, have identified key features of such organizations that face an unpredictable and always connected world and have developed an integrated model defined by the dynamics of interactions between internal, heterogeneous agents and transversal networks (Lucescu and Avasilcăi, 2020 forthcoming). The way some organizations try to solve newly occurred problems often seem to create more confusion therefore it is legitimately prevailing to further cast a look upon issues, practices, bias and barriers to the development of agility in business context.

Purpose – the aim of this paper is to pinpoint some of the issues, barriers and practices that may impair presence of AOc and thus, developing an agile organization.

Methodology/approach - An extensive literature review and observation are conducted to identify and confirm the characterization of the determined issues. Once identified, they will be in a structured catalogue.

Findings – The literature review comprises 2000+ references published between 2001 and 2020. We have selected 100+ papers for full consideration and have identified 8 key factors for instilling AOc, 3 types of barriers with subsequently 8 hidden ones and 5 common errors in creating conditions for AOc to thrive. We examine 14 organizations in Romania to determine the relevance of the selected issues.

Research limitations/implications – When the Romanian literature is reviewed, there is no other study examining AOc, except for conceptual studies regarding technical software methodology and approach.

Practical implications – For this reason, it can be stated that our study will contribute empirically both to related literature and to the business world.

Key words: AOc, common errors, development of agility

Introduction

Pre-pandemic, most mature companies have already gone through many rounds of changes: reorganizations, mergers, decentralizations, new IT platforms, new CRM systems, new reward systems. However, the organizations confronting the realities brought by the global health crisis find themselves challenged by unprecedented demands. In order to survive, organizations detach themselves from the logic of what they knew how to do before and move in new directions from which to react from a different mindset. It is not a binary type change, but a collective transformation and of course, some organizations have a longer way to go than others, depending on the starting point (culture, market, strategy). To resist, organizations are forced to initiate emerging strategies, exploiting and building “transient competitive advantages” (McGrath, 2013). In our study we largely aim to explore the mechanisms of agility (Lucescu, Avasilcăi, & Bagiu, 2018) in an organizational context (AOc) at a level best described by being agile, living those values and principles. To a certain extent AOc seems to contribute to better navigate the turmoil of deep uncertainty by virtue of sensing the market signals (the reactive facet),

internal decision-making mechanisms and flexibility (the proactive facet) in providing the response expected by the market (Lucescu and Avasilcăi, 2020 forthcoming)

In this context, the aim of this paper is to pinpoint and spot some of the issues, barriers and practices that may impair presence of AOc and thus, developing an agile organization.

Developing AOc is not about adopting a new set of tools, processes or procedures at team level, but it is rather about how the whole organization develops the ability to respond and regrettably, almost any event in the life of any organization comes to impede the autonomy of the teams.

We have developed in our research an integrated model defined by the dynamics of interactions and functions between internal, heterogeneous agents and transversal network from an AOc perspective. In most companies AOc requires significant remodelling and changes - it is about breaking dependence, about managing without an ego, alignment of values and flows, and this type of transformation depends entirely on top management (Cattmeyer, 2019). A team will always be limited in its agility by the very organizational circumscription to which it belongs and AOc manifests differences depending on the structure of the organization. The traditional ones are designed around a static, silo-type hierarchy, with clear levels and functions and the decisions are taken from top to bottom. Those organizations that develop AOc instil the vision and purpose, are characterized by networks of operational teams that accomplish tasks in fast cycles of learning-decision-application and decision makers become those who are closer to information, with the intention of combining speed and adaptability with stability and efficiency (McKinsey, 2019). Agility in an organizational context does not proclaim a particular practice; it is the quality of the organization and its people to notice changes in the market, to be received and to continuously learn to adapt their processes and procedures to innovate and respond in accordance with new customer behaviours.

Fig. 1. Attracting and integration of the functions from the perspective of agility in an organizational context. Proposed model.

The management style reforms its mechanisms, aims towards other goals, manifold principles and it is based on a multiform set of values that disrupt the assumptions, attitudes and habits of generations before. In fact, the way we think about work is changing. Hence the new paradigm of organizations as living organisms. What will the world of work look like in the coming decades is a legitimate question to ask starting today. Either way, the whole process of designing the new way of working requires a mixture of tripartite: a mental transformation, one of abilities and another of behaviours. By influencing the paradigm, skills and behaviours will ultimately influence the organizational culture as a whole.

Issues that impede fostering agility in organizational context

In a turbulent market all organizations, large or small, are vulnerable; none has the guarantee of supremacy and none is sheltered from any level of invincible performance. From the researched case studies (Bertolini, Duncan, & Waldeck, 2015), there are three perspectives that emerge as responsible for market failure in the most obvious way: the business model, the internal capabilities and general customer preferences. Along with them, we note as a particular issue the overconfidence that top management displays when asked about people's differences in perceptions of change.

Not every failure dislocates functions, but with every new change in the environment, new threats come along conditioning organizations to respond with new skills. Only a seamless unlearning- relearning process can confirm whether or not that organization has the ability to change. AOC is very much about putting one's own beliefs to the test, which goes further, in depth, in culture, in the “metaphorical field of the organization that exercises control over the organization through unconscious / preconscious / conscious beliefs, presumptions and paradigms. This field is an organizational system of symbolic significance” (Huțu, 1999) and plays a key role in any failure to implement agile steps, actions or projects. (Findings of the 13th State of the Agile Report, 2019).

Fig. 2. The role of organizational culture in the success of organizational transformation.
Adapted model -Findings of the 13th State of Agile Report

Failure to start from a scout-like mindset to overcome cultural resistance seems the number one issue to adopting an agile mentality.

On the other hand, agility in the organizational context, as it is, often co-exists with other traditional approaches to organizational development. Many large companies rely on decades-old systems and methodologies that carry the legacy of control. Well-established practices, hierarchical structure, well designed processes, roles, benefits, expectations support the need to control work in itself, employees feel constrained and limited by rules that no longer help them perform their tasks or unleash their creativity and impede the fast needed cycle of sense-decide- respond, as agility marker.

Hidden barriers to the development of agility in organizational context

Fig. 3. Hidden barriers to the development of agility in organizational context. Proposed model.

The personal agenda prevents managers from giving up control, so the ideal of transparency in communication turns into supervision: in order to make the performance visible, tickets are introduced for any step, linking visibility to control (Wolpers, 2019) as the culture stays unchanged: decisions continue to be made by those who do not understand technology (Feynman, 1997).

A cognitive error in implementing agility is to see it as a framework for change. Organizations typically adopt sprints and sprint-associated artefacts and ignore other components of the framework, which are usually values of agility. As long as values and culture do not align with agile beliefs, adopting a package of agile practices is like improving only in spot places, leaving the organization the same, untouched. Transformation is about the transition towards being agile, adoption is about utilizing some tools (Cannon and Elford, 2017). The symptoms that the transformation did not really happen and that values are not quite lived are made visible by the absence of some key attributes:

- team members do not have the psychological security (Edmondson, 2019) to initiate discussions on issues and blockages are not openly discussed,
- tasks are assigned and planned by the traditional command centre and not by the responsible team,

- no tests / prototypes are initiated in order to reveal the problems,
- communication is one-way, teams report, do not discuss,
- stars are valued, not the team (Hansen, 2010),
- implicit information and knowledge are carefully preserved (key skills and information are seen as a subject of information management - Knowledge management - KM),
- agility is addressed as a methodology that people should apply,
- outside experts are reluctantly considered.

It is common to see in organizations different agendas of interests facing objectives or resources. Integrative mechanisms (Hansen, M., Ibidem, p. 93) that promote the alignment of goals and values do not always work, and the proposed strategies are abandoned with a disappointment that deeply contaminates the climate. This type of conflict is a fibre in the fabric of organizational life since the division of labour (Durkheim, 1863, apud Hansen, M.). Members of a group develop their own conflicting interests and values. Groups become prisoners of their own mental models, biased, and have difficulty appreciating / accepting the perspective of other groups / organizations, so their alignment becomes a difficult and sometimes painful process. Hazy or manifest, some conflicts become chronic, at their root prevailing the structural differences between expert combatants, their perspectives, beliefs and identity. There is a refined and sophisticated literature on behavioural theories about conflict around goals, feedback, mental models, but the neuroscience of communication (Turnbull, 2015) targets the depth of mechanisms that give identity to actors in organizations.

Distinct blockages in creating agility conditions in an organizational context

Fig. 4. Distinct blockages in creating agility conditions in an organizational context. Proposed model.

A mental block causes a series of incomplete connections that consume considerable amounts of mental energy in the expected chain of decisions (Rock, 2009):

- lack of vision,
- fundamental attribution errors (correspondence bias),
- lack of involvement (comes from non-communication of personal benefits at C-level and /or middle management level)

- lack of transparency,
- holding errors back (Syed, 2017),
- disconnecting transversal departments collaboration,
- hindering access to customers by the sales department.

These constraints lead to stress, exhaustion and disengagement in work and organization.

In 2015, after investigating more than 2,500 companies in 94 countries, Deloitte places employee exhaustion at the top of the concerns of 65 percent of executives in 94 countries. In 2016 there was a record of disinterest in work of 68 percent- a rate that has improved in the last year by up to five points in some areas of the world (Oehler & Adair, 2019) and this is very well understood for several decades.

Other companies avoid this dilemma by cutting costs, tax cuts, offshore, creating an illusory prosperity, but which undermines the real value of the organization.

Collaboration occurs when people from different departments work together in combined teams to perform a common task or to offer each other important help. Rarely does collaboration work naturally (Hansen, M. p. 34) because leaders themselves raise barriers. The problem arises when managers focus exclusively on its objectives, the organization becoming a sum of departments arranged as in a puzzle, a kind of fiefdoms, or bunkers.

The barriers are therefore personal. Factors that block collaborative behaviours belong to ego jurisdiction: thirst for power, arrogance, defensive attitude, fear, pride.

On the other hand, there are organizations that learn how to work better for its people and for those to whom they address it now form a vast global movement that transforms work itself and makes the world we live in an agile world (Denning, 2016).

Common errors in creating conditions to foster agility in an organizational context

Fig. 5. Common errors in creating conditions to foster agility in organizational context. Proposed model.

1. misaligned motivations

To the question <why do you want to become an agile organization?> (McKinsey, 2017), the surveyed managers answered:

- to give a faster response in the market (82 percent)
- to become more efficient (65 percent)
- to improve the predictability of deliveries (49 percent)

If we compare these answers with the benefits of AOc (“Why Agility Pays”, 2015):

- overcoming competitors through the ability to learn

- creating the conditions for autonomy, excellence, purpose, thus attracting talent from the market
- improving ROI, minimizing risks

we notice the misalignment of the motivations:

- little or no support from the board to become a learning organization you have to assume that it is a continuous process, with no return.

2. the organization displays an inertia that, paradoxically, ensures its success: it provides stability, and it serves the middle level management. The What's in It for Me syndrome and the question of why middle management would support an agile paradigm appear. Taylorism is still successful; autonomy implies another type of approach: coaching, mentoring, and only the change of title does not work.

3. self-sufficiency - we know what we have to do- this error is often found at the level of beliefs: so far it has worked, it will work from now on, and the failure is rationalized in terms of external environment: something happened in the market / exchange rate / policy, etc., no one could have anticipated this.

4. simplification- it's nothing complicated, we take a model and apply it to us (Linders, 2016).

Conclusions

Not all organizations need to become agile in organizational context in order to have a culture of excellence and deliver value to customers. However, if skills change and technology continues to advance as big players invest, then organizations need to learn to swiftly adapt and take fast decisions in response to customers changing behaviours.

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